

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Improved medium for efficient anther culture of some indica rice hybrids

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Anther culture of high heterotic F₁ hybrid rices could be used to isolate doubled-haploid true breeding lines. Assuming that heterosis in rice is due primarily to dispersion of genes in parents that display directional dominance, some doubled-haploid lines derived from heterotic F₁s theoretically should equal F₁ hybrid performance. Such doubled-haploid lines could be used for commercial cultivation or as parents of second-cycle F₁ hybrids.

To test the validity of this assumption, we cultured anthers of four IRRI-bred heterotic F₁ hybrids.

An improved culture medium increased anther culture efficiency in the F₁ hybrids tested. Two media formulations differing in source of N were used (Table 1). Medium MSN is a

Table 1. Media composition.^a

Constituent	SK-1 (mg/liter)	MSN (mg/liter)
KNO ₃	3150	2830
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	—	463
KH ₂ PO ₄	540	170
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	150	440
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	185	185
MnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	22.3	4.4
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10	1.5
H ₃ BO ₃	6	6.2
KI	1	0.8
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.25	0.25
CuSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.025	0.025

^aConstituents (mg/liter) in common: 27.85 Na₂·EDTA + 37.25 Fe·SO₄·7H₂O; 2 glycine; 100 inositol; 2.5 niacin; 2.5 thianine HCl; 2.5 pyridoxine; 500 casein hydrolysate; 0.75 2, 4-D; 2.5 NAA; 0.75 kinetin; 40,000 sucrose; 8,000 agar. The generation medium consisted of MS basal medium supplemented with 1 mg NAA, 1 mg BAP, 0.5 mg kinetin, 30,000 mg sucrose/liter.

Table 2. Callus induction and green plant regeneration in anther calli of hybrid rices induced in SK-1 and MSN media.

Hybrid ^a	Anthers plated (no.)	Anther calli		Calli transferred (no.)	Calli regenerating				
		no.	%		Green plants		Albino plants		
					no.	%	no.	%	
<i>SK-1</i>									
H-1	2216	146	6.1	114	42	36.8	27	23.6	
H-2	1698	82	4.8	52	23	44.2	20	38.4	
H-4	2855	308	10.7	220	74	33.6	55	25.0	
H-5	1572	69	4.3	41	5	12.2	4	9.7	
Total	8401	605	7.2	427	144	33.7	106	24.8	
<i>MSN</i>									
H-1	2147	298	13.8	278	20	7.1	65	23.3	
H-2	2495	275	11.0	228	15	6.5	45	19.1	
H-4	2900	406	14.0	284	55	19.3	80	28.1	
H-5	2176	125	5.7	69	6	8.6	12	17.3	
Total	9718	1104	11.3	859	96	11.1	202	23.5	

^aH-1 = hybrid 1 (IR54752 A/IR2797-125-3-3-2 R), H-2 = hybrid 2 (IR54752 A/IR64 R), H-4 = hybrid 4 (IR54752 A/ARC11353 R), H-5 = hybrid 5 (IR46830 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R).

blend of Murashige and Skoog's and Chinese N6. SK-1 contains N, mainly as nitrate, among other modifications. Vitamins, amino acids, sucrose, and hormones were similar for both media.

Response (% anthers producing visible calli) was better in MSN medium for all the hybrids (Table 2), in some cases more than twice that in SK-1. In the regeneration medium, however, calli induced in SK-1 averaged 200% higher regeneration of green plants. In IR54752 A/IR2797-125-3-3-2 R and IR54752 A/IR64 R, the difference was 400%.

Among 859 anther calli induced in MSN, 96 green plant-regenerating calli were identified. As many as 144 green plant-regenerating calli were obtained from only 427 calli induced in SK-1.

Other media formulations also were tested. In all, more than 35,000 anthers were cultured, resulting in more than 300 green plant-regenerating anther calli. About 700 plants transferred to the field reached maturity.

The SK-1 culture medium appears promising for alleviating the poor anther culture efficiency of indica rices. □

Optimum distance of isolation for hybrid rice seed production

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Maintaining purity of parental lines and F₁ hybrid seed is the most important factor in hybrid seed production. One way to maintain seed purity is to adequately isolate plots used for producing hybrid seed.

We laid out an experiment at IRRI 1987-88 to determine the isolation

distance that would prevent contamination. A seed production plot of IR64 (1,250 m²) was used as the pollen source. At 10 d before flowering, eight potted plants of the CMS line IR54752 A were placed at different distances (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200, 225 m) in two directions (northeast and northwest) from the pollen source (per anticipated wind direction during flowering). Weather records for the experimental periods of both years are given in Table 1.

Pollen fertility was measured at flowering and four plants showing